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The Contribution of Art and Design to the Leather Handicrafts of Bangladesh and Its Production Oriented Process

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ABSTRACT

Leather technology has a lot of potential in Bangladesh which is why I am thinking about its development projects and trying to find some ways and solutions. So that in the future Bangladesh will be in a stronger position in leather technology and will be able to earn domestic and foreign exchange. I have taken a plan to work with Erato Nolji in Bangladesh motivated by some purpose. The raw material of leather product that is available in our country from developed countries is much cheaper and the chances are much higher here. When the raw material of a product becomes very cheap, it is very easy to produce that product and sell it at a good price, but there are also many obstacles that my main purpose is to solve. Below are some of the motives I have set for our potential leather industry products business in Bangladesh.

Keywords

Authentic leather product development, Bangladeshi leather technology, Framework, International quality making, product Marketing

1. Bangladeshi leather technology

Bangladesh has been associated with the leather art and design culture since time immemorial as a thriving and prosperous industry. Our handicrafts are very old in terms of design, and we are very rich in this industry as Leda handicrafts are deeply involved with the culture of Bangladesh. At present, leather industry is a high-quality industry for which every country attaches importance to this industry. The leather industry of Bangladesh is very advanced, and the skins of our country are of very high quality but due to the lack of sophisticated leather our industry is not able to move forward properly. Even after this, the leather factories in

Bangladesh have gained a lot of reputation in different countries and are leading the way in our country with high quality products. With high quality design and sophisticated touch, I have some plans to take our country's leather industry forward that I will try to implement.

2. Literature review

If we can study and work on the leather handicrafts of Bangladesh properly, we will be able to make a great contribution to the leather industry in the future. The leather industry of Bangladesh has been going on for many ages through a beautiful craft. To give an accurate description of the leather industry, our Bangladesh art and the culture are deeply involved. The art and designs used in the leather industry of Bangladesh are of high quality and are in keeping with our culture. I think one of the two places in our Bangladeshi leather industry is shoes and bags. The leather industry in our country is a very old industry but no advanced measures have been taken to date. Due to which we are lagging far behind in terms of such a promising industry but this industry in our country is very promising and prosperous. Among the various types of industrial factories in our country, the leather industry factory is the most popular and has achieved business success. There are few mills in the leather industry which are exporting to our country and abroad, but they are not perfect for us.

So, I am more interested in advancing the leather industry in our country. Many high-quality products are made from different types of animal skins in our country but due to lack of marketing and use of advanced technology we are lagging far behind, but our country's skins are of much better quality. Considering how to take the leather industry forward in our country, I have adopted some of the plans that I will raise today.

3. Framework

We need to build a process to move forward in the development of the Letter industry if not only handicrafts but also using technology and those are what I am trying to describe. I salvage the reasons behind the backwardness of our forward in the future.

We need to re-use our products in our products by restoring all the technical education art and designs that have been used to make our old tradition cell leather industry significant. We need to reintroduce all the leather designs that are associated with culture and civilization through new art. We need to bring something new through the integration of our new designs with the old leather handicrafts of our country so that the new society will gladly accept them. If we can modernize our leather industry by using advanced technology while retaining our culture along with hand leather industry, then we will go further. We can take the help of online to showcase our handicraft art related to our culture and civilization to the whole world and by doing so we will be able to come up with better solutions and ideas.

4. Authentic design develop

New design and innovation in old products are a very important thing. To get the right price for a product, you must keep an eye on its design development, and you must keep the product innovative from

before to next. If there is anything that can be provided to the clients outside of the usual leather products, they will buy it at an attractive price. I first notice how the leather of our country's animals are being preserved and how they are being collected. Because if our raw material is not collected properly then our product will never be well formed. Therefore, through modernization, it is necessary to decide for the preservation and collection of skins using advanced technology.

The right price of leather should be bought and collected without falling into the hands of any organization and they should be tested and tested to see how important they are and how useful they are to make a product. If we can buy raw materials at the right price and at a good price, then we can do profitable business. Those who are interested in making leather products and have enough knowledge should make the right product with the skins so that there is no error. We need to collect those artisans who are interested in making these products and are very skilled. Not only hands-on education but also how other countries have taken their leather industry so far. In addition to using high quality state-of-the-art leather technology, we also need to think thoroughly about the designs and show the new designs to the customer.

We can get something better by discussing with the countries that have advanced in the leather industry through advanced technology. We can acquire technology knowledge from outside the country to impart knowledge of advanced leather industry to our artisans. We can layout the products we have designed first and then shape them with leather. When it comes to designing, we must try to bring designs from our culture and civilization by targeting a foreign country. Then we can show outsiders something new in the field of design and introduce new types of products to our culture through leather technology. We can do better by following the brands that have come a long way in the leather industry in our country and sharing about the latest innovations through them.

The leather needs to be properly processed and cleaned so that our products are good. In the case of handicraft industry, all the paints and equipment's that were used in our country need to be restored and made available to the artisans with a touch of modernization. We will try to fully present our culture and culture in our leather handicrafts in case any country should do any art and design in line with their own culture. Only when we take our leather industry forward in handicrafts can the whole world know about our leather industry heritage and our old civilizations if we have a conference of our civilization and culture with our leather industry. First of all we have to choose the skins properly for a good production.

The leather needs to be chemically cleaned and deodorized and then we must take them into production. If the customer likes our products, they will give us a fair price so that we can benefit. And they must be designed by designers in such a way that they are very popular with people. When it comes to shoe production, we need to make sure that the leather is hard and strong, and that we need to educate the craftsman about how the shoes are made. In 80% of the cases, the leather used to make the bags is very thin and strong, so we must use all the leather for the bags that are needed for the bags. We can also make winter jackets using high quality leathers which are well oiled in the market. We also must look at the design.

Leather products that are very strong and are more expensive than any other product need to be designed so that customers can use them with ease. If there are any abnormalities in a leather, we must test it first because after going into production, we will not be able to work with leather that is damaged and unusable. We will continue to use cow dung and lambskin in our productions which are strong and durable and much cheaper than these. We can also use snake leather among the expensive products which is very famous all over the world but in that case, we must set a fair price for a product. Snakeskin is not very valuable and readily available which can cause our product prices to increase a lot

Before we make our products, we need to think about which markets we will sell them to and how we will deliver them to the customer.

If we can properly observe our products and bring them to the attention of the people in the right way with their design and quality, people will surely gladly accept our products.

5. Marketing and Theoretical Work

Advertising has made a huge contribution in the present age. If your product is good, then you must advertise and if your product is not suitable for the market then you can sell your product in the market through advertisement. In addition to the leather business, we also need to strengthen our marketing team so that our products are properly oiled at the right price and people can have an idea about our products. I think marketing can cause a business to lag far behind which is why we must make a strong contribution to marketing so that we can sell our products while maintaining quality. When it comes to making and selling leather products, I will follow some of the marketing and advertising policies that I am describing.

Before we process the products and make the products, we need to keep in mind who our customers are and how much they are worth.

Online marketing is one of the biggest contributors in today's world and we can get a lot of customers if we can spread the word about our business online through a website.

In television media and FM radio and we can advertise our ads and product quality, then our products are likely to be sold at the right price.

We will give accurate descriptions of our products in the advertisements and accurate descriptions of what kind of chemicals and what kind of leather has been used in them so that our customers get the right information before buying their product

We can advertise our products in a variety of weekly magazines and dailies so that people can see and study them. If we can accurately record everything about our products there and show people, our other by providing pictures then people will buy from us at the right price.

Domestic and foreign customers who are interested in buying our products at wholesale should bring a special discount and a leaflet with our product details so that they are interested to go with us for a big deal.

We provide wholesale in various big stores or markets inside the country as well as inform those who are interested in buying our products outside the country about the quality and quantity of our products. So that besides earning income in our country, we can earn foreign exchange.

If we can sell our products properly outside the country, then our country will be famous and our communication with foreign countries will be much better, and we will also get the opportunity to buy their products in our country at lower prices.

6. International quality making

When a product is of international standard then the market value will increase, and people will be aware and interested in the quality of that product. The quality of raw materials and the use of technology equipment must be avoided in making international quality products. I think we will benefit a lot if we make our country's leather industry usable properly then we must follow our work as well as our outputs. If we don't get the right output for every business and industry, then that work is meaningless and unprofitable. Raising cattle is a very common thing in our country and by extracting hides from them we can get the raw material of our industry at a very low price

When we get advanced raw materials at very low prices, we can spend our money on technical and advanced designs. If we can make a lot of beautiful leather products in our own country, then we can sell it at a good price in our own country and abroad so that we can make a lot of profit Our country's leather products are very cheap, but we are lagging in this industry due to our inability to manufacture high quality exportable products. So, if we focus on this industry properly and try to develop our hard work and talent, then we can benefit from it in a good way. The raw materials we need to use the designs are very easily available in our country now we just must try to make beautiful products using high quality machinery. There are very few companies in our country working on the leather industry which are not profitable in that way. If we monitor this industry more, we can earn a lot of money from here. If we follow our personal designs and keep the quality intact, I think any country would be interested in working with us on leather products and we would be able to accept them at the right price. To communicate with a foreign customer, we need to put our marketing online team in a strong position and by hiring people who are skilled in this type of work, we will maintain our foreign relations and decide to deliver our products to them. We will sell our leather products first inside our country so that the people of our country can use good quality products at the right price and then when our business grows, we will plan to sell them outside the country.

7. Objectives

Main objective has been to work on the leather handicrafts that were and still are associated with the culture and civilization of Bangladesh and to make it a profitable business in the future. One of my main objectives is to develop our culture and civilization in front of the whole world through the development of leather handicrafts. To achieve this goal, I have formulated a plan to take our handicrafts culture forward through modern machinery along with handicrafts. Our traditional handicraft industry has been rich for a long time so we can make it today by maintaining the culture through handicrafts and modern machinery, through which it is possible to use the leather of our handicrafts and to form them in the right design plan and to produce extra dimensions to our beautiful products. In the past our leather industry was very advanced and if we can properly study the descriptions of our handmade leather industry, we get from our heritage then we hope for something better in the future. I will share with you some future of our leather handicrafts and formulate a plan to move them forward based on our experience. We need to study old leather handicrafts and try to figure out how to make them stand out. We need to be aware of how and why our traditional handicrafts were formed and work on their significance.

8. Conclusion

I have tried to give a brief description of our Bangladeshi leather industry here and what I will do in the future, according to my plan here. There are many types of questions that I will try to solve in the future. When I do my final submission, I will try to solve your questions here. There are several new plans that need to be made to reshape a structured art, which is a little difficult at the present time, but very important for the future.

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